

MAROON-X: A New Earth-Finder Spectrograph for Gemini North

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One of the most exciting areas of exoplanet research is identifying and characterizing nearby habitable planets. The ultimate goal is to make a credible search for life on planets outside of our Solar System, and key to realizing such a comprehensive exoplanet science program is an instrument for measuring radial velocities to sufficiently high precision. To meet this need, the University of Chicago's Bean Exoplanet Group has constructed a next-generation radial velocity spectrograph called MAROON-X for use as a Visiting Instrument at the Gemini North telescope (the international Gemini Observatory is a Program of NSF's NOIRLab).

An important goal of exoplanet science is to measure masses and radii for a large enough sample of low-mass planets that robust statistics emerge. Transiting planet finder missions that are designed to exploit the synergy between radial velocity and transit techniques include the *Kepler*/K2 mission; NASA's *Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite* (TESS) mission; ESA's *CHaracterising EXOPlanet Satellite* (CHEOPS) mission; and ESA's *PLANetary Transits and Oscillations of stars* (PLATO) mission, now set for 2026. The many new small transiting planets that will be identified by these missions present an enormous opportunity to expand the study of planetary statistics into the regime of planet bulk compositions—if we can measure the masses of these objects using the radial velocity method.

Design Goals

MAROON-X was designed for high-precision radial velocity (RV) measurements (~ 1 m/s or better) of fainter stars than is possible with existing spectrographs. Existing

radial velocity instruments become very inefficient around $V = 12$ th magnitude, and objects with $V > 13$ th magnitude are essentially out of reach for all but the most intense campaigns. The instrument was also designed to study planets in the habitable zone of the very lowest-mass M dwarfs (those with $M_{\text{star}} < 0.3 M_{\odot}$). In contrast to solar-type stars, the habitable zones of M dwarfs are close-in enough so that planets in this region have a significant chance of transiting, making them feasible targets for transit spectroscopy observations to characterize their atmospheres. The lowest-mass M dwarfs are intrinsically very faint, however, and current instruments can achieve 1 m/s precision only for the handful of these stars within a few parsecs (e.g., Proxima Centauri and Barnard's Star). To take advantage of the opportunities offered by transiting low-mass planets around low-mass M dwarfs, we need high-precision radial velocity measurements for these stars out to 20 pc (Deming et al., 2009, PASP, 121, 952).

MAROON-X

The MAROON-X team has carried out detailed simulations to identify the optimum wavelength range to observe low-mass M dwarfs for radial velocity measurements. They find that the red part of the optical spectrum contains comparable radial velocity information as the near-infrared for stars down to masses of $0.10 M_{\odot}$ ($T_{\text{eff}} \approx 2,600$ K), because radial velocity measurements depend not just on the number of collected photons but also on the spectral line density. Although M dwarfs are brighter around 1 micron (μm), the very high line density at shorter

wavelengths more than compensates for the difference. This means that the optimum wavelength intervals for radial velocity measurements of solar-type and low-mass stars are not very different, and they can be spanned by a single spectrograph.

Thus, MAROON-X is a red-optical (500–900 nanometers [nm]), high-resolution ($R = 80,000$) spectrograph capable of delivering high-precision radial velocities with an intrinsic instrument stability of < 0.5 m/s. The instrument's core spectrograph is fiber-fed (including a fiber for simultaneous calibration), enclosed in a vacuum chamber, and

thermally and mechanically isolated from its environment (Seifahrt et al., 2016, SPIE, 9908, 990818). The spectrograph's design is based on an asymmetric white-pupil approach, which re-images and then re-collimates all dispersed beams after the echelle grating into a common pupil to minimize the diameter of the cross-disperser and camera. This design variation has been used successfully on other instruments, for example, on the High-Resolution Spectrograph (HRS) at the Southern African Large Telescope. The table provides a summary of MAROON-X's expected properties at Gemini North.

MAROON-X Main Characteristics

Spectral resolution	$R = 80,000$
Acceptance angle	FOV = 0.77" at the 8m Gemini North telescope
Wavelength range	500 nm–900 nm (in 56 orders)
Number and reach of arms	Two (500–670 nm and 650–900 nm)
Cross-disperser	Anamorphic VPH grisms
Beam diameter	100 mm (at echelle grating), 33 mm (at cross-disperser)
Main fiber	100 μm octagonal (CeramOptec)
Number and type of slicer	3x pupil slicer
Slit forming fibers	Five $50 \times 150\mu\text{m}$ rectangular (CeramOptec), including sky and calibration
Inter-order and inter-slice spacing	≥ 10 pixel
Average sampling	3.5 pixel per FWHM
Blue detector	Standard 30 μm thick $4\text{k} \times 4\text{k}$ STA 4850 CCD (15 μm pixel size)
Red detector	Deep-depletion 100 μm thick $4\text{k} \times 4\text{k}$ STA 4850 CCD (15 μm pixel size)
Calibration	Fabry-Perot etalon for simultaneous reference (fed by 2nd fiber)
Exposure meter	Chromatic
Environment for main optics	Vacuum operation, 1 mK temperature stability
Environment for camera optics	Pressure sealed operation, 20 mK temperature stability
Long-term instrument stability	0.7 m/s (requirement), 0.5 m/s (goal)
Total efficiency	11% (requirement) to 15% (goal) at 700 nm (at 70th percentile seeing)
Observational efficiency	S/N=100 at 750 nm for a $V=16.5$ late M dwarf in 30 minutes

Figure 1: Small subsection of a solar spectrum recorded with MAROON-X at the University of Chicago. For comparison we overplot the same region from the solar atlas of Wallace et al. (2011, *ApJS*, 195, 6) obtained with the Fourier Transform Spectrometer (FTS) at the McMath-Pierce Solar Telescope, reduced to the spectral resolving power of MAROON-X ($R=80,000$). In the bottom of the figure we show the simultaneously recorded spectrum from the MAROON-X etalon calibrator. The spectra have been flat-fielded and are blaze corrected.

The primary wavelength calibrator for the instrument is a stabilized Fabry-Perot etalon, traced to the hyperfine transition of rubidium. This device delivers a comb-like spectrum of about 500 bright and unresolved lines per spectral order with frequencies traceable to a few cm/s (Stürmer et al., 2017, *JATIS*, 3, 025003). In addition, an automated solar telescope was available in the lab to deliver solar light to the spectrograph (see Figure 1), allowing the team to test and improve the data reduction and radial velocity analysis pipeline.

In January 2017, KiwiStar Optics delivered the core spectrograph and the blue wavelength arm to the University of Chicago. This was installed in a chamber with temperature control to better than 20 milliKelvin. All the expected characteristics of the spectrograph (e.g., resolution, scattered light, and efficiency) were confirmed with lab measurements. First tests with the etalon calibrator demonstrated that even over the limited spectral coverage of the smaller and less stable lab detector system, the science and calibration fibers track each other to better than 20 cm/s

over timescales of minutes to days. The high line density and exquisite stability of the etalon allow for unprecedented stability vetting and calibration at a level otherwise offered only by a much more complex and expensive laser frequency comb.

Integration at Gemini North

The instrument team, with input from Gemini staff, designed a front end for MAROON-X to connect to an instrument port, while the instrument itself will reside in the Pier Lab. This front end was successfully commissioned at Gemini North in 2018, in advance of shipping the instrument from Chicago (Figure 2).

In April 2019, MAROON-X passed its pre-ship acceptance in Chicago and was disassembled to begin its voyage to Hawai'i, to be reassembled and aligned in the thermally controlled enclosure that had been prepared for it in the Pier Lab. Uncrating and inspection began on 6 May, with assembly and positioning of large items (such as the cryo-

Figure 2: Right: Andreas Seifahrt (left) and Julian Stürmer (both University of Chicago, where MAROON-X was constructed) beneath the MAROON-X front end installed on the bottom instrument port at Gemini North. (Credit: International Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/S. Yu)

Figure 2: The internal organs of the MAROON-X front end in the lab in Chicago, preparing for the acceptance test. (Credit: University of Chicago/A. Seifahrt)

stat) taking place over the next few days. During the week of 13 May, the optics were unpacked, integrated, and aligned. The work went extremely smoothly, thanks to the outstanding instrument team and the assistance of the skilled Gemini day crew, but commissioning was delayed a few months due to the Maunakea Access Road closure from July to December 2019. Fortunately, the team were flexible, and we were able to resume work on the instrument as soon as access was available.

MAROON-X has now completed one commissioning run, using 20 hours of telescope time over eight nights in December 2019. Two critical measurements, the simultaneous etalon calibration and the stability tracing of the etalon,

were unfortunately not ready at the time of the December run. Although the RV performance tests will thus not yet reflect the final performance of MAROON-X, the data were very promising (Figure 3). Because the instrument performed well, we are able to offer MAROON-X for general high-resolution spectroscopy to the Gemini User Community in the 2020B semester, and we look forward to offering it for high-precision RV measurements in the very near future.

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Figure 3: Plots of the signal to noise ratio (SNR) measured for two stars observed during the MAROON-X commissioning run in December 2019. For each order, the measured SNR is shown for the combined flux of all three object fibers. These data are not fully calibrated, but they provide a sense of what we may expect from a typical observation.

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